

IN VITRO EFFICACY OF ANTI-TICK ACTIVITY OF ENTOMOPATHOGENIC FUNGI AGAINST *RHIPICEPHALUS MICROPLUS*

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Abstract

In India, control of ticks is solely relied on the usage of chemical acaricides and their continuous use has been resulted in occurrence of resistance against them. Owing to wide spread resistance against acaricides, it becomes necessary to explore alternative methods of tick control. Amongst the alternative methods, the entomopathogenic fungi are well-documented for their capacity to infect various tick species and hence can be used as biological control agents to curb the tick menace. For this purpose, fully engorged freshly dropped female *R. microplus* were procured from cow sheds of Mhow (M.P.). For *in vitro* trials, working concentrations of powder of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* were prepared in milk and water. The adult immersion test was carried out for the assessment of anti-tick activity of entomopathogenic fungi. The mortality (19.44%) of adult female ticks with significant decrement in the reproductive index (0.35) along with inhibition of oviposition (44.77%) was recorded in ticks treated with *B. bassiana*. Adult female ticks treated with *M. anisopliae* showed lowest reproductive index of 0.569 with highest inhibition of oviposition of 7.94. Lowest hatchability of 35.67 and 73.42% was noted in eggs laid by adult female ticks treated with *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*, respectively. Significantly low ($P < 0.01$) hatchability was noticed at every concentration of *B. bassiana* than that of *M. anisopliae*. Depending on the findings of the present investigation, it can be deduced that, the fungi like *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* can be inducted as a part of integrated pest management owing to growing concern of resistance against chemical acaricides.

Keywords: *Beauveria bassiana*, Cattle tick, Entomopathogenic fungi, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Rhipicephalus microplus*

Introduction

At present, the tick control has become arduous not only owing to the growing concern of resistance as the resistance is prevailing against practically all the acaricides but also owing to the non-availability of commercial non-chemical acaricides. Therefore, alternative approaches need to be tried using organisms like fungi and bacteria which are effective against arthropods ([Kaaya et al.2011](#), [Ren et al. 2016](#), [González et al. 2016](#), [Aw & Hue 2017](#)). Amongst these, the entomopathogenic fungi are widely known natural enemies of arthropods and hence can be utilized as biological control agents against ticks (Chandler et al. 2000). During the host infection, *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* produce hydrolytic extracellular enzymes, including proteases and chitinases, which probably degrade the tick's cuticle (St. Leger et al. 1986,1996). Many studies have proved the potency of fungal agents against ticks (Kaaya & Hassan 2000, Samish et al. 2004, Fernandes & Bittencourt 2008, Leemon & Jonsson 2008, Sun et al. 2011, Rao & Narladkar 2018a, b). Therefore, for effective control of ticks, use of biological weapons becomes necessary owing to large scale development of resistance against chemical acaricides. In future, such kind of biological control measures will be a part of integrated pest management which will reduce the use of chemical acaricides. Therefore, the present investigation was designed to analyse the efficacy of anti-tick activity of entomopathogenic fungi against *R. microplus*.

Materials and Methods

Fully engorged freshly dropped female ticks (*R. microplus*) were procured from nearby areas of Mhow. Collected ticks (>250 to 300) were brought to the Department of Veterinary Parasitology, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, Mhow and were maintained at the temperature of 28°C and 85±5% relative humidity (Ghosh & Azhahianambi 2007). Eggs deposited by ticks of each group were kept in a glass tube and were kept in a biochemical oxygen demand incubator in order to hatch the larvae. The fungal powders of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* were procured from Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani (Maharashtra). For all *in vitro* trials, working concentrations were prepared as 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 g powder + 5 ml milk + 1 litre of water. The methodology described by Srivastava et al. (2008), Kaaya & Hassan (2000) and Rao & Narladkar (2018a, b) was followed with minor modifications. In each diluted concentration of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*, 6 female ticks of 6 replicates each were dipped for 5 minutes and dipped ticks were dried on filter paper and subsequently kept in petri dishes, these petri dishes were kept in desiccators which were kept in BOD incubator maintaining a temperature of 28 ± 1°C and 85 ± 5% RH. The death rate of ticks was observed up to 14 days post-treatment and egg masses deposited by the ticks were also noted down after 24 hrs till 14 days of treatment. Those ticks which did not deposit eggs after 14 days were considered as dead. Egg laying process of all survived ticks including ticks of treatment and control group was monitored till the completion of egg laying period. The individual tick was considered as dead only when movement was not evidenced even after pricking with the pin and the mortality percentage was recorded. Similarly, if not dead, for recording the egg laying capacity and egg's hatchability of treated ticks, weight of

eggs laid was recorded and was compared with control ticks. The reproductive index (RI) and inhibition of oviposition (IO) was calculated (Sharma et al. 2012). Graph Pad Prism 9 software was used to draw the regression curve of probit mortality and IO against log values of concentration (Finney 1962). The slope of regression curve and the correlation coefficient was recorded. Regression equation $Y = mX + C$, where m is the slope of the curve, C is the y intercept, x is the log value of concentration of entomopathogenic fungi and Y is the probit value of percent mortality of adult ticks. The lethal concentration for 50% (LC50) and 95% (LC95) values of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* against *R. microplus* were determined by applying regression equation analysis to the probit transformed data of mortality and IO. For evaluation of the anti-tick activity of entomopathogenic fungi, one-way ANOVA was employed. The t-test was employed to analyse the potency of fungal acaricides on hatchability of eggs deposited by females treated with entomopathogenic fungi.

Results and Discussion

B. Bassiana

In this bioassay, the ticks were monitored for duration of 14 days for recording the mortality, RI and IO of ticks. When the ticks were exposed to different concentrations of *B. bassiana*, viz. 4,5,6,7 and 8g, the mortality was recorded as 0.00, 8.33, 13.89, 13.89 and 19.44%, respectively. The RI values were noted as 0.43, 0.46, 0.38, 0.39 and 0.35 in ticks treated with different concentrations like 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 g, respectively. Upon treatment of ticks with different concentrations like 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8g, the IO values were observed as 25.48, 18.46, 36.78, 35.02, and 44.77%, respectively. When the female ticks were treated with different concentrations like 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8g, the hatchability of eggs deposited by treated ticks was recorded as 63.58, 57.08, 54.50, 49.42 and 35.67, respectively (Table 1).

The regression graph of probit mortality plotted against log values of progressively increasing concentration of *B. bassiana* is displayed in Fig. 1. Dotted lines in the regression curve represent 95% confidence interval. Values of slope of mortality (95% CI), goodness of fit (R^2), LC50 (95% CI) and LC95 (95% CI) of *R. microplus* against *B. bassiana* are presented in Table 2. The slope of mortality (95% CI) and R^2 were documented as 0.0625 ± 1.641 (-0.54-9.89) and 0.73, respectively. The equation was utilized for demonstration of LC50 (95% CI) and LC95 (95% CI) values which were recorded as 11.33 (10.90-11.78) and 25.36 (23.33-27.58) ppm, respectively.

The regression graph of probit inhibition of oviposition plotted against log values of progressively increasing concentration of *B. bassiana* is displayed in Fig. 2. Values of slope of IO (95% CI), goodness of fit (R^2), LC50 and LC95 of *R. microplus* against *B. bassiana* were recorded as 2.01 ± 0.87 (-0.76 - 4.78), 0.64, 10.17 (9.30 - 11.14) and 67.41(55.22 - 82.28) ppm, respectively (Table 3).

In the present experimental design, 19.44% mortality was observed when the adult female ticks were treated with the highest concentration (8 g/L) of *B. bassiana*. Reproductive index (0.35) was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) reduced when the adult female ticks were treated with *B. bassiana* (8 g/lit). Further, the significant difference in the values of RI was in evidence in ticks exposed to different

concentrations of *B. bassiana*. Significantly high ($P \leq 0.05$) inhibition of oviposition (44.77%) was noted at the concentration of 8 g/lit than other concentrations of *B. bassiana*. Lowest hatchability of 35.67% was noted in ticks treated with the concentration of 8 g/lit which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) with other concentrations of fungi (Table 1).

Table 1: Reproductive index, inhibition oviposition and hatchability of *R. microplus* treated with *B. bassiana*

Conc. (g)	Number of ticks	Weight of ticks (mg) (Mean \pm SE)	Mortality of ticks (%)	Egg mass (mg)** (Mean \pm SE)	RI**	IO (%)*	Hatchability (%)**
4	36	101.28 \pm 4.64	0.00	43.67 ^c \pm 1.93	0.43 ^{bc}	25.48 ^{bc}	63.58 ^b \pm 1.55
5	36	140.39 \pm 2.48	8.33	64.78 ^b \pm 4.82	0.46 ^b	18.46 ^c	57.08 ^c \pm 1.74
6	36	119.53 \pm 5.08	13.89	45.72 ^c \pm 2.98	0.38 ^{cd}	36.78 ^{ab}	54.50 ^c \pm 1.77
7	36	106.11 \pm 4.97	13.89	41.39 ^{cd} \pm 1.96	0.39 ^{bc} _d	35.02 ^{ab} _c	49.42 ^d \pm 2.08
8	36	95.31 \pm 1.47	19.44	33.17 ^d \pm 2.45	0.35 ^d	44.77 ^a	35.67 ^c \pm 2.14
Control	36	156.92 \pm 2.33	0.00	84.83 ^a \pm 4.47	0.54 ^a	00.00	98.00 ^a \pm 0.34

RI-Reproductive Index and IO- Inhibition Oviposition

* = Significant ($P \leq 0.05$)

**= Highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$)

a, b, c, d, e = Means with different superscript in column differ significantly

Simple linear regression

Figure 1. Individual regression curve showing probit mortality in AIT against log concentrations of *B. bassiana* in *R. microplus*

Table 2: Mortality slope, R², LC50, LC95 values with 95% CI of female *R. microplus* treated with *B. bassiana*

Concentration (ppm)	Log Conc.	Probit mortality	Slope ±SE (95% CI)	R ²	LC50 (95%CI)	LC95 (95%CI)
4	0.60	2.54	0.0625±1.641 (-0.54-9.89)	0.73	11.33 (10.90-11.78)	25.36 (23.33-27.58)
5	0.70	3.72				
6	0.78	4.03				
7	0.85	3.72				
8	0.90	4.22				

Simple linear regression

Figure 2. Individual regression curve showing probit inhibition of oviposition in AIT against log concentrations of *B. bassiana* in *R. microplus*

Table 3: IO slope, R², LC50, LC95 values with 95% CI of female *R. microplus* treated with *B. bassiana*

Concentration (ppm)	Log Conc.	Probit IO	Slope ±SE (95% CI)	R ²	LC50 (95%CI)	LC95 (95%CI)
4	0.60	4.34	2.01±0.87 (-0.76-4.78)	0.64	10.17 (9.30- 11.14)	67.41 (55.22- 82.28)
5	0.70	4.10				
6	0.78	4.66				
7	0.85	4.62				
8	0.90	4.87				

M. anisopliae

The mortality was not in evidence in ticks treated with *M. anisopliae*. The RI values were recorded as 0.593, 0.592, 0.591, 0.584, and 0.569 in ticks exposed to different concentrations of *M. anisopliae* like 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8g, respectively. Upon exposure of different concentrations of *M. anisopliae* like 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8g, the IO values were noted as 4.06, 4.25, 4.36, 5.53 and 7.94% respectively. Hatchability of eggs deposited by treated ticks was recorded as 87.25, 85.67, 82.92, 76.75 and 72.42, when the female ticks were exposed to various concentrations, viz. 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8g, respectively (Table 4).

The regression graph of probit inhibition of oviposition plotted against log values of progressively increasing concentration of *M. anisopliae* is presented in Fig. 3. Values of slope of IO (95% CI), goodness of fit (R²), LC50 and LC95 of *R. microplus* against *M. anisopliae* are presented in Table 5. The slope of IO (95% CI) and R² were documented as 0.96 ±0.36 and 0.70, respectively. The

equation was used to determine the of LC50 and LC95 values and which were recorded as 264.93 (220.68 – 318.06) and 12135.54 (40064.05 – 91827.61) ppm, respectively.

The lowest reproductive index (0.569) was observed at the concentration of 8 g/L when the adult female ticks were treated with this fungus. In this case, the highest inhibition of oviposition (7.94%) was noted at the concentration of 8 g/L which differed significantly ($P \geq 0.05$) with all the treatment groups except at the concentration of 7 g/L. Lowest hatchability of 72.42 % was noted in ticks treated with the concentration of 8 g/lit which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) with other concentrations of fungi (Table 4).

When the effect of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* on the hatchability of eggs treated adult females was compared by applying the t-test, significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) low hatchability of eggs was noticed in adult females exposed with every concentration of *B. bassiana* than every concentration of *M. anisopliae* demonstrating the higher efficacy of *B. bassiana* than *M. anisopliae* (Table 6).

Similarly, the workers like, Leemon and Jonsson (2008) observed virulence of *M. anisopliae* against ticks. Sun et al. (2013) recorded efficacy of *B. bassiana* against engorged female ticks. Rao and Narladkar (2018a, b) recorded mortality of adult ticks, reduction in egg laying capacity and hatchability of eggs treated with *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*. Aboelhadid et al. (2018) observed 100% mortality of larvae in ticks treated with *Verticillium lecanii* and *B. bassiana*.

The mortality of ticks treated with entomopathogenic fungi appears to be due to germination of conidia and formation of appressoria as the adhesion, germination and production of conidia are considered as important virulence factors against arthropods. After penetration of arthropod cuticle by the germ tubes, fungi rapidly attack the internal organs and kill these arthropods. Release of mycotoxins is also considered responsible for arthropod mortality. The *B. bassiana* produces many of the cuticle degrading hydrolytic extracellular enzymes like chitinases and B-1, 3 glucanases. Toxic metabolites secreted by fungi might be responsible for their establishment and progression of the disease caused by them. Further, *B. bassiana* produces subtilisin-like proteases and chitinases in *R. (B.) microplus* (Campos et al. 2005). The *M. anisopliae* invades the host through the cuticle by mechanical pressure, due to appressorium formation and degradation by the synergistic action of hydrolytic enzymes like proteases, chitinases and lipases (Gindin et al. 2009). The *M. anisopliae* penetrates the arthropod body through the cuticle and reproduces in it and might be responsible for reduced reproduction of infected organism (Quesada-Moraga et al. 2004). As per Kaaya (2000) and Quesada-Moraga et al. (2004), the *M. anisopliae* reduces the oviposition of the treated ticks and causes interrupted hatching. Samish et al. (2001) reported *M. anisopliae* infection in subsequent developmental stages and also recorded prevention of egg laying by engorged *R. sanguineus*.

Table 4: Reproductive index, inhibition oviposition and hatchability of *R. microplus* treated with *M. anisopliae*

Concentration (g)	No. of ticks	Weight of ticks (mg) (Mean ± SE)	Mortality of ticks (%)	Egg mass (mg) (Mean ± SE)	RI	IO (%) [*]	Hatchability ^{**} (%)
4	36	147.81±0.41	00	87.64±0.55	0.593	4.06 ^b	87.25 ^b ±1.54
5	36	142.19±0.54	00	84.14±0.28	0.592	4.25 ^b	85.67 ^{bc} ±1.26
6	36	143.36±0.98	00	85.44±0.79	0.591	4.36 ^b	82.92 ^c ±1.43
7	36	142.44±0.72	00	84.25±0.83	0.584	5.53 ^{ab}	76.75 ^d ±1.07
8	36	141.33±0.69	00	83.44±2.24	0.569	7.94 ^a	72.42 ^e ±1.26
Control	36	147.44±0.52	00	91.14±0.28	0.618	00.00	98.17 ^a ±0.21

RI-Reproductive Index and IO- Inhibition Oviposition

NS =Non significant

* = Significant (P≤0.05)

**= Highly significant (P≤0.01)

a, b, c, d, e = Means with different superscript in column differ significant

Simple linear regression

Figure. 3. Individual regression curve showing probit inhibition of oviposition in AIT against log concentrations of *M. anisopliae* in *R. microplus*

Table 5: IO slope, R², LC50, LC95 values with 95% CI of female *R. microplus* treated with *M. anisopliae*

Concentration (ppm)	Log Conc.	Probit IO	Slope ±SE (95% CI)	R ²	LC50 (95%CI)	LC95 (95%CI)
4	0.60	3.26	0.96±0.36	0.70	264.93 (220.68-318.06)	12135.54 (40064.05-91827.61)
5	0.70	3.28				
6	0.78	3.29				
7	0.85	3.40				
8	0.90	3.59				

Table 6: Effect of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* on hatchability (%) of treated female *R. microplus*

Concentration (g)	Number of treated eggs	<i>B. bassiana</i>	<i>M. anisopliae</i>
4**	200	63.58 ^b ± 1.55	87.25 ^a ±1.54
5**	200	57.08 ^b ± 1.74	85.67 ^a ± 1.26
6**	200	54.50 ^b ± 1.77	82.92 ^a ± 1.43
7**	200	49.42 ^b ± 2.08	76.75 ^a ± 1.07
8**	200	35.67 ^b ± 2.14	72.42 ^a ± 1.26
Control ^{NS}	200	98.00 ± 0.34	98.17 ± 0.21

NS =Non-significant

* = Significant (P≤0.05)

**= Highly significant (P≤0.01)

^{a, b}= Means with different superscript in row differ significantly

Conclusion

The mortality (19.44%) of adult female ticks with significant reduction in the reproductive index (0.35) along with the highest inhibition of oviposition (44.77%) was recorded with the highest concentration (8 g/lit) of *Beauveria bassiana*. Negligible mortality (2.8%) of adult female ticks with the reproductive index of 0.550 and 5.05% inhibition of oviposition was observed in ticks treated with *M. anisopliae*. Lowest hatchability of 35.67 and 73.42% was noted in eggs laid by adult female ticks treated with *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*, respectively. Significantly low (P<0.01) hatchability was noticed at every concentration of *B. bassiana* than that of *M. anisopliae*.

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